

RESEARCH OF OIL COKE PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract: Currently, the process of obtaining coke products from oil and petroleum products is increasing day by day. This article explains the process of obtaining coke products. Coking raw material is usually high molecular oil in most cases residues - tars, thermal cracking residues, pyrolysis soot, deasphalting asphalt, as well as highly flavored distillate crude that improves coke quality materials (thermal and catalytic cracking heavy gasoils) are used.

Key words: Oil and oil products, physicochemical properties, production, coke products, processing, promising technology,

Production of petroleum cokes, metals, non-ferrous metals, and some chemical products production, production of graphite materials, production of carbides and iron alloys used as a returner on output.

Coke is formed in liquid phase thermal processes. In some cases, for example, in thermal cracking, it is considered an unpleasant by-product. On the other hand, there are specially developed processes for obtaining coke, which are of great importance in the national economy. It is used as a reducing agent in chemical technology, in metallurgy for the production of anodes, in aviation and rocket technology (Be 2 C; TiC), in the production of abrasives and refractories (SiC; B₄ C; TiC), in nuclear power (V 4C, ZrC), structural carbon - is used to obtain graphite materials [1].

Petroleum coke is a solid substance with a high carbon content and a density of 1400-1500 kg/m³. The atomic ratio of C:H in coke is 1.1-4. It is produced as a result of liquid phase thermal processing of oil residues according to the scheme below will be:

Arenas → tars → asphaltenes → coke → graphite

Alkanes, cycloalkanes and alkenes are also capable of forming coke, however not directly, but in the processes of deep changes and aromatization. Arenas transition to coke and then to graphite is legal from the thermodynamic point of view, because it occurs with a decrease in the free energy level. In the sequence benzene → naphthalene → anthracene → pyrene → graphite, the reserve of free energy per one carbon atom (in kJ) decreases in the following order:

20,6 → 19,8 → 18,8 → 16,8 → 0.

Heavy oil residues serve as raw material for coke production. In coking - gas, gasoline, diesel fractions and coke are obtained. In tar coking, 11% gas, 16% gasoline, 49% coke distillate, 24% coke are obtained. The quality and productivity of coking products depends on the composition of raw materials and the process depending on the driving conditions. During the coking of high-sulfur petroleum residues the content of the formed coke is up to 4%. This is coke as fuel is used. Coking is a combination of several processes (evaporation, complex molecular includes compounds - simpler breakdowns, condensations). Fast or slow evaporation affects coking [2].

For example:

a) substances formed as a result of evaporation from the place where the process is taking place if it is removed at high speed, less coke is produced, and more coke distillate is produced.

b) Evaporation is slow at high pressure. Therefore, such coking gas and coke production increases, while coke distillate production decreases.

Increasing temperature also reduces coke formation. 490,14 atm. is the optimal condition of the coking process. The majority of petroleum coke consumers have a high need for low-sulfur coke. Therefore, it is necessary to send residues containing no more than 0.5-0.8% sulfur to coking. Technological schemes of complexes that can obtain low-sulfur coke from sulfur raw materials have been developed, but the cost of coke obtained according to these schemes is much higher than that of coke produced from low-sulfur residues.

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